

SUMMARY OF CHANGES BETWEEN PROTOCOL VERSIONS

Study Title	Supportive Care and Antibiotics for Severe Pneumonia among Hospitalised Children (SEARCH): A Pragmatic Randomised Controlled Trial
Trial Registration	Clinical Trials.gov: NCT04041791 PACTR: 202106720981298 .
Latest protocol version and date	Version 1.8 dated 29 August 2023
Initial protocol version and date	Version 1.3 dated 20 January 2019

From Protocol version and date	To Protocol version and date	Changes Amendments	Comments
Version 1.3 dated 20 January 2019	Version 1.4 dated 15 April 2019	<p>Update to Archiving and Record Retention Section</p> <p>The protocol was updated to indicate that study documents would be retained for a duration of 10 years after conclusion of the trial.</p>	This was <u>the first protocol amendment</u> .
		<p>Change in Sponsor's authorised representative on the front page of the protocol</p> <p>The sponsor's authorised representative name was changed from Head of Department to Director of Research Services.</p>	
Version 1.4 dated 15 April 2019	Version 1.5 dated 01 October 2022	<p>Addition of new investigators</p> <p>14 new investigators were added to the protocol.</p>	This was <u>the second protocol amendment</u> .
		<p>Addition of new study sites</p> <p>New sites were added to the protocol.</p> <p>These were: Thika Level 5 hospital, Nakuru Level 6 hospital, Migori County Referral hospital and Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral Hospital.</p>	

SEARCH TRIAL
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From Protocol version and date	To Protocol version and date	Changes Amendments	Comments
Version 1.5 dated 01 October 2022	Version 1.6 dated 20 February 2025	<p>Addition of new study objective: The new objective assesses health providers costs and perceptions of caregivers and healthcare workers towards the study interventions</p> <hr/> <p>Addition of new investigators Two new investigators were added to the protocol.</p>	This was <u>the third protocol amendment.</u>
Version 1.6 dated 20 February 2025	Version 1.8 dated 29 August 2023	<p>Change in Sponsor’s contact details University of Oxford’s contact details were updated in the protocol</p> <hr/> <p>Addition of new investigators Four new investigators were added to the protocol.</p> <hr/> <p>Addition of new study sites New sites were added to the protocol. These were: Kisii Teaching and Referral Hospital, Mama Margaret Kenyatta Hospital and Kerugoya County Referral Hospital.</p> <hr/> <p>Addition of Kenyatta National Hospital- University of Nairobi (KNH-UoN ESRC) in the ethical considerations section of the updated trial protocol.</p>	This was <u>the fourth protocol amendment.</u>